

Aquatic Symbiosis Genomics Project Leadership

This document holds a record of the team leads at the Wellcome Sanger Institute and genome collection hubs who should be considered coauthors of publications arising from the Aquatic Symbiosis Genomics project (<https://www.aquaticsymbiosisgenomics.org/>).

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